

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING TO STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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Abstract. The article examines the teaching of a foreign language to students with disabilities at a university. It also offers methods and techniques for effectively teaching these students a foreign language.

Key words: foreign language, motivation, students with disabilities, methods, techniques.

Currently, there is a tendency for the health of children and adolescents to deteriorate, and the number of people with disabilities has increased. However, each individual strives to get a good education and realize themselves in life. In general, there is currently an increase in the interest of applicants with disabilities in education, social interaction within various social groups and communities [3]. It is generally accepted that proficiency in a foreign language at a level that allows solving every day and professional problems is a competitive advantage for a modern university graduate. In this regard, the problem of obtaining higher education by students with disabilities in general, and mastering a foreign language in particular, is especially relevant.

To successfully master both the entire curriculum and a foreign language, students need motivation. At the same time, the issue of motivation for learning a foreign language among people with disabilities is acute, since learning it is especially difficult due to the health of students. It is necessary to work on maintaining motivation regularly. First of all, it is necessary to carry out educational activities based on specific limitations in the physical condition of students; it is necessary to use an individual approach. To prevent a motivational decline, the teacher should provide statistics on people with disabilities who have already completed their studies, develop an interest in learning the language through the topics covered during the study of the subject, which helps students form a different view of their own limitations, the topics and topics to be learned must be personally significant, for this it is necessary to refine the educational and methodological literature by adding relevant topics to the main program proposed in the teaching and methodological kit. The teacher should also establish communication links with the group and create a favorable psychological atmosphere in the classroom, as a result of which the student should learn to set goals and find ways to achieve them, learn to objectively evaluate the results of their actions, even if the training is remote. It is very

important to create situations of success in students. It is also recommended to use musical accompaniment in foreign language classes in order to maintain the proper level of motivation for studying the subject [1]. In the process of teaching, it is important for the teacher to do everything possible so that the student, regardless of pathology, can perceive and remember information [2]. To do this, it is necessary to identify the dominant type of information perception. It is known that according to the type of information perception, individuals are divided into visual, auditory and kinesthetic, therefore, during the first lessons, it is worth identifying which type a particular student belongs to and then using methods and techniques that are effective for each student, thus showing an individual approach to teaching a foreign language.

However, in the context of implementing the curriculum within the framework of group training at a university, providing new material in an individual approach mode is not always possible. In this regard, it is recommended to combine several ways of presenting the material that meet the needs of students with certain types of information perception. In the future, the teacher is required to frequently reproduce lexical units audibly, provide visual supports, use associative exercises that are effective for memorizing unknown vocabulary and repeating the material studied. These techniques help students not only to learn the material within the framework of the reproductive approach, but also promote independent study of the proposed topic, which develops an active position in learning a foreign language, increases the level of motivation for learning, and creates positive dynamics of academic results. Learning a foreign language requires constant and long-term work on it, active involvement in intellectual activity, development of such mental cognitive processes as attention, thinking, memory, all this leads to the awareness of the value of the process of learning a foreign language. To organize the practice of foreign language speech, the teacher should involve students in foreign language competitions within the university or faculty, organize viewing of films in the language being studied, followed by a discussion of the main points in a foreign language in the form of "question-answer" and / or monologue. This technology includes the use of communicative methods of teaching a foreign language, and the use of ICT, which meets the challenges of the time.

Computer technologies have long been used in teaching, and in working with students with disabilities, they are an essential teaching tool, thanks to which students communicate with teachers, receive the material they need to learn in the form of video lectures, audio, visual aids, tables, diagrams and other

visual aids, complete assignments, check them using an automated system, for example, in an electronic educational and methodological course and/or with the help of a teacher, solve test and creative tasks, have the opportunity to record their video/audio and send them to the teacher for checking, study on an electronic training simulator and perform a large number of operations daily to master and practice educational material [1]. All this has led to the fact that the use of ICT is an integral means of teaching students with disabilities, which gives them the opportunity to integrate into the educational process as much as possible along with standard students and continuously increases the motivation of students to study a foreign language.

Obtaining higher education, mastering a profession for students with disabilities is currently achievable due to the presence, continuous development and improvement of the inclusive education system. Inclusion allows these students not only to develop their intellectual abilities necessary to achieve certain academic results and obtain professional skills, but also to improve all the necessary personal characteristics in the process of socialization, active integration into the educational process and extracurricular activities together with normative students.

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